

Cosmic Inflation and the Incense Stick Analogy: A Thought Experiment

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Introduction

The origin of the universe remains one of the deep mysteries in cosmology. The widely accepted Big Bang theory describes the universe's expansion from a singularity.

This paper talks about a thought experiment that not only illustrates this idea but also hints about the possibilities that there could be more than the big bang than we know it. It also gives an idea that what **Dark Energy** could do to our universe.

The Thought Experiment

Suppose there is a tightly packed and well-lit room. Now we place an Incense Stick at the centre of the room and let it burn for a few minutes until the smoke is fully distributed in the room. Now we let a Person X go into that room and observe the smoke. Person X is special as he doesn't have the ability to differentiate the smell of things but he can smell things. His task/purpose is to theorize that how the smoke came to be distributed throughout the room.

- **The Observations and Theories of Person X**

After inspecting the room, Person X would see no physical evidence of the incense stick itself because it's been fully consumed and turned into smoke. Based on his observations Person X might theorize that some kind of **explosive event** took place, which created the smoke and spread it throughout the room. Possibly he could think a fire ignited suddenly or that an explosion occurred, propelling smoke in all directions. But if Person X is lucky enough then he could make the

correct observation: that the source of the smoke was an incense stick which slowly burned and released smoke into the air.

This exact type of reasoning is similar to how scientists theorize the **Big Bang** and the rapid expansion of the universe. Just like Person X, scientists don't have the direct access to the original event but observe the "residual" effects—the **Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation (CMBR)**, which is the afterglow of the early universe's expansion. This faint radiation fills the entire universe much like the smoke fills the room, and it offers key evidences about the early stages of the universe's evolution.

The "Reverse Modelling" of Smoke and the Early Universe

Now, let's add a twist to Person X's investigation. Suppose Person X, decides to reverse model the smoke. He might try to trace the smoke back to its origins. He could theorize that the smoke must have originated from a **highly concentrated, tightly packed sphere of smoke**, which then exploded to spread throughout the room. The explosion would have occurred because this tightly packed mass of smoke had accumulated too much **energy** and needed to expand rapidly. This reverse model mirrors the idea of the **Big Bang** in cosmology—an incredibly dense, hot, and concentrated state of the universe that exploded outward due to an immense amount of energy. This model is strikingly similar to the **cosmic inflation** theory, where the early universe was incredibly small and dense, and the rapid expansion was triggered by high energy. Just as Person X might visualize the smoke being compressed into a small sphere before the explosion, cosmologists think of the universe's early state as a singularity—a point of infinite density, before it expanded in the Big Bang event.

This thought experiment raises an intriguing question: **just as the smoke in the room might have been influenced by the combustion of incense stick, could the Big Bang also have had external factors involved?** It invites us to consider whether our current understanding, based on the CMBR, might be missing some critical pieces or

external influences. To dive deeper into this analogy, let's explore specific similarities between the physical properties of the smoke and the universe's behaviour during and after the Big Bang

- **Similarity in Element of Kinetic Energy and Rapid Expansion**

Just as the smoke from the incense stick begins with a high kinetic energy moving quickly outwards from the stick's burning end, in the same way universe's rapid inflation involved space expanding at speeds greater than the speed of light. The early universe like the smoke was moving quickly and uniformly, and this kinetic energy was a key factor in creating the structure of the universe we see today. Over time, just as the smoke cools and becomes evenly distributed, the universe gradually cooled, leading to the formation of galaxies, stars, and the cosmic structures that fill it.

- **Similarity in Cosmic Fluctuations and Density Variations**

Just as the smoke in the room might have small areas of higher or lower density that creates patterns and irregularities in same way the universe also had tiny density fluctuations in its early moments. These variations, imprinted in the CMBR, were stretched to cosmic scales during inflation and eventually became the seeds for the large-scale structures like galaxies and clusters of galaxies. In our analogy, if Person X were to look closely at the smoke, he might see swirling patterns or areas where the smoke is denser. These represent the primordial density fluctuations that led to the formation of the universe's structure.

Dark Energy

In our thought experiment, the air in the room can represent dark energy—a medium that is invisible but important for the smoke's behavior. As the incense stick burns, the smoke rises and spreads because it is lighter than air, much like galaxies and matter in the universe are 'pushed apart' by the expansive influence of dark energy. The air, though unseen and taken for granted, governs the smoke's

movement and distribution, just as dark energy silently governs the accelerated expansion of the cosmos.

To Person X, the smoke's upward movement might seem like a property of the smoke itself. However, we know that this movement is due to its interaction with the air. In the same way, dark energy interacts with the fabric of spacetime, driving galaxies farther apart. Without air—or dark energy—the smoke would remain static, just as the universe's expansion would not accelerate without dark energy.

Conclusion

The incense stick analogy offers a powerful framework for understanding the Big Bang and cosmic inflation by translating abstract cosmological ideas into simple, everyday phenomena. This analogy highlights the similarities between the distribution of smoke and the observable universe, such as the role of kinetic energy in expansion, the emergence of density fluctuations, and the reliance on indirect evidence like the CMBR to reconstruct cosmic history.

However, it also opens path for deeper inquiry. Could there have been an external trigger for the Big Bang, akin to the combustion of the incense stick? Are our current interpretations of the CMBR missing nuances about the origins of the universe? This thought experiment not only simplifies complex ideas but also challenges us to expand our understanding, encouraging us to look beyond conventional models in pursuit of a more comprehensive cosmological picture.

Citations

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